

DETERMINANTS OF EMPLOYEE PERCEIVED TURNOVER INTENTION: A STUDY ON PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN DAMBI DOLLO

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Abstract

The study aimed to examine the determinants of employee perceived turnover intention in private secondary schools in Dambi Dollo town. The identified independent variables for this study were career path development, job satisfaction, salary consideration, employee engagement, work-life balance, and working environment, while employee turnover intention was used as the dependent variable. A causal research design, specifically a sectional design, was employed. Both primary and secondary data served as sources of information. The census survey method was utilized for data collection. To gather data, a structured questionnaire was administered. After data collection, analysis was conducted using the statistical tool SPSS. To ensure the reliability and validity of the instrument, a pilot study was performed by distributing 20 questionnaires to teachers at Dambi Dollo public secondary schools who were not part of the main study. The data analysis revealed that career path development, salary consideration, job satisfaction, and work-life balance significantly influence turnover intention. In contrast, emotional engagement and work environment were not significant factors in determining employee perceived turnover intention in this study. Sex, age, and educational level of teachers had an insignificant impact on perceived turnover intention. However, the marital status of teachers was found to have a significant effect on perceived turnover intention. Based on these findings, important recommendations were made to address these issues.

Keywords: Employee, Turnover, Intention, Engagement, Environment, Work-life Balance.

JEL classification Codes: J63, J28, M12, M54, I25

1.1. Introduction

Employee turnover intention has some remarkable consequences for any type of profit or nonprofit-making organization. In the human resource management field, the issue of turnover intention is becoming a serious issue. If the employee's decision to leave his current job is changed to the actual turnover, then new workers must be procured and prepared. It is additionally expected to consider

the time and cost required for another worker to be adequately efficient. Employee turnover is a significant consideration in organizations worldwide. According to Currivan (1999), "Turnover is a behavior which describes the process of leaving or replacing employees in an institution". Flippo (1980) defined turnover as "It is the ratio of the number of workers that had to be replaced in a given time period to the average number of workers". Turnover has a considerable impact on an institution's performance, as it should be properly addressed and measured. Employee turnover intention is defined as an employee's intention to voluntarily change jobs or companies. According to Gomez-Mejia (2000), employee turnover intention can influence the turnover decision in two ways. It may directly lead an employee to exit even when other job opportunities are not available. Also, it may influence actual turnover indirectly by leading the employee to search for new job alternatives, thus resulting in the likelihood of termination. Employee turnover intention does not have the same meaning as actual employee turnover because there is a difference between the actual leaving and the intent to exit (Mobley, 1977).

Employee turnover intention can lead to a decrease in morale of employees who are using their efforts as much as they can. Employee turnover can diminish the efficiency of the organization, and in the same way, the cost of hiring, training, and development, and the substitution of the old with new employees will increase. Additionally, turnover affects the organization in such a way that it will lose skilled and competent employees and diminish the morale of the existing employees (Flippo, 1980). Employee turnover happens when individuals leave their work or organization for several reasons. There are two ways in which turnover happens in the schools. The first one is when teachers are going to leave the teaching profession, which is Attrition. The second one is when teachers are moving or transferring from one school to another, which is called Migration. Therefore, both have considerable costs and require time because there is a decrease in staff that must be replaced (Ingersoll, 2001).

For schools, skilled human power is the most essential contributor and also a resource. Because schools can achieve their objectives effectively through their qualified and competent teachers. Teachers are the key staff in an educational system since they contribute to the delivery of good education. According to Ayalew (2009), teachers are means in the accomplishment of educational goals. The educational system can be developed only through the contribution of teachers who are qualified and competent. A loss of these qualified and competent teachers is a real worry for the education system in general. Employee turnover in schools is not the only problem of developing countries; it is also a problem of developed countries for the development of the educational system. The study conducted by Ingersoll (2001) in America, at the end of every five years, one or two teachers leave their school. Also, African countries are highly affected by teachers' turnover. World Bank (2007) stated in its study that current teacher attrition rates are in the range between 5 and 30 percent in different countries of Sub-Saharan Africa.

The problem of employee turnover in schools is also observed in Ethiopia by various studies conducted in different regions of the country. These studies indicated that teachers are leaving their teaching profession or moving from one school to another. For example, current studies show that in Ethiopia, teachers in various regions are exiting their schools for different reasons (Temesegen, 2005, and Motuma, 2006).

Since the teachers play a major role in the delivery of quality education, several well-experienced and qualified teaching staff left teaching voluntarily due to several reasons in the current year. Theoretically, there are many factors influencing teachers to leave their jobs. That is, turnover is not something that happens out of nothing. Specifically, voluntary teaching staff turnover occurred

largely due to inadequate salary, Poor working conditions, inappropriate recruitment, promotion, policies, inadequate induction program, poor administrative support, and poor communications. (Destefano,1989). Dereje (2007) stated that ways for solving the teacher turnover problem are improving working conditions, induction & mentoring of new teachers. Abeshu (2003) also stated that the ways of reducing turnover in school staff are long-term awards, social outings, and participatory decision-making systems that encourage and facilitate the involvement and planning activities, open and timely communication.

In today's competitive business world, it is considered an important task to manage employee turnover for any organization. Managing turnover successfully is very critical to achieving the organization's long-term goals. Employee turnover is a concern for all organizations, but historically, it plagues the field of education at a particularly high rate, with more than one in three new teachers leaving the classroom within their first three to five years of employment (Ingersoll & Merrill, 2012).

1.2. Study Gap

Several studies were conducted in Ethiopia on employee turnover in secondary schools in several areas of the country. For instance, Temesgen (2005) found that the percentage of teachers who are degree holders in secondary schools of the Gambella region was 20%. Similarly, in secondary schools of the Oromia region, a study conducted by Motuma (2006) stated that in the years from 2001 to 2004, the turnover rate was 17%. Additionally, as Alazare (2007) stated in his study, the turnover rate of employees in Yeka sub-city of Addis Ababa secondary schools in 2003 and 2004 was 14.1% and 11.2 % respectively. It is believed that teachers are the major employees of schools who can influence the quality of education. Different scholars and experts have been studying the determinants of employee turnover intention. According to Boran (2011), the basic determinant of employee turnover is psychological factors like organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Another study conducted in South Africa by Neinaber and Masibigiri (2012) on determinants of employee turnover intention. Their study indicated that factors for employee turnover intention were rigid and poor work environment, absence of training, lack of recognition, lack of better job offer, poor career path, limited job opportunity, low salary, and absence of organizational justice. In recent studies, the determinants of employee turnover intention are categorized as teacher characteristics, school administrative factors, teachers' job satisfaction, commitment, and characteristics of students. There is a gap in studies conducted in Ethiopia regarding the impact of employee emotional engagement on turnover intention. The research in Ethiopia related to the determinant of employee turnover intention in secondary schools has failed to explore how employee emotional engagement influences teacher turnover intention. Especially in schools, teachers have to be emotionally engaged because as they are emotionally engaged in teaching, their intention to leave the school will decrease. Mason & Matas (2015) defined employee emotional engagement as an employee's intensity and willingness to invest emotionally toward positive organizational outcomes.

There are a few studies conducted in Ethiopia in the area concerning only the government secondary schools. Therefore, there should be further study on the area of employee turnover in private secondary schools because the factors that determine employee turnover at government and private secondary schools are not identical. A study by Dronkers and Robert (2003) found the differences between the public and private secondary schools in terms of student characteristics, school composition, deliberate school choice, different conditions for teaching-learning and school administration, different school climates, and a stronger core curriculum. Most of the research conducted in Ethiopia has focused on actual employee turnover, and very little research has been conducted on the intention in the area of determinants of employee turnover intention of private

secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone. Therefore, the researcher was attempting to fill the gap by examining the determinants of employee perceived turnover intention.

The general objective of the study is to identify the determinants of employee perceived turnover intention, a study on private secondary schools in Dambi Dollo Zone. Accordingly, the study addressed the following specific objectives.

- ✚ Evaluate the factors that determine employee perceived turnover intention in private secondary schools in Dambi Dollo Zone.
- ✚ Investigate the factors significantly influencing the employee perceived turnover intention in private secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone.
- ✚ Examine the impact of demographic profiles of private secondary school teachers in Dambi Dollo Zone on their perceived intention to turnover.

1.3. Research Hypothesis

H₁: Job satisfaction has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo.

H₂: Workplace environment has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone

H₃: Career path development has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone.

H₄: Employee engagement has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone.

H₅: Salary has a significant impact on employee turnover perceived intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone.

H₆: Work-life balance has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone.

H₇: Gender has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone.

H₈: Education level has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone.

H₉: Age difference has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone.

H₁₀: Marital status difference has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention in secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone.

1.4. Significance of the Study

Retaining experienced and qualified employees, especially teaching staff, has great importance to education planners and policymakers to realize the educational objectives of the country. Accordingly, this study is useful and timely in identifying determinants of perceived employee

turnover intention in advance by giving suitable recommendations for school administrators and policy makers. This study is timely because the results of this study will help to frame future policy decisions regarding employee retention and provide a closer look into the effects of determinant factors of turnover intention for school administrators and policy makers. This study will hopefully increase employee retention rates in the educational sector and reduce financial losses of private secondary schools in Dambi Dollo Zone.

2. Conceptual Framework

Fig 2.1: Conceptual framework of the study

3. Research Methodology

For this study, the researcher used a causal research design. A cross-sectional research design was used because information was collected from the population only once to assess the relationship between independent variables and perceived employee turnover intention. Therefore, this study adhered to the causal research design. The researcher used both primary and secondary sources of data. Primary sources of data for this study were collected through a structured questionnaire from the target population, whereas secondary source of data for this study was collected from the HRM department about employees’ general information that was necessary for this study. The target population of the study was all the teachers working in private secondary schools in Dambi Dollo Zone.

The model specification of the study is as follows:

$$Y = a + \beta x$$

Where, y = dependent variable; a = intercept; β = slope (coefficient) of independent variable x

$$EPTI = a + \beta_1 JS + \beta_2 WE + \beta_3 CPD + \beta_4 SC + \beta_5 WLB + \beta_6 EE + U$$

Where: EPTI = Employee perceived turnover intention

JS = Job satisfaction

WE = Work environment
 CPD = Career path development
 SC = Salary consideration
 WLB = Work-life balance
 EE = Employee engagement
 DD = Demographic determinants
 U = Stochastic Disturbance

The quantitative data obtained through the questionnaire were analysed using the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) software version 22. The Multiple regression analysis was applied to determine the effect of selected variables

Reliability Test

With the help of SPSS version 22, the reliability of these questionnaires was tested.

Table 3.1. Summary of Reliability Study

Variables	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
IV	Career Path Development	0.753
IV	Job Satisfaction	0.795
IV	Salary Consideration	0.854
IV	Employee Engagement	0.759
IV	Work Life Balance	0.839
IV	Working Environment	0.761
DV	Employee turnover intention	0.855

Source: Own Survey, 2025

Validity of the Instruments

Content Validity: The content validity of the questionnaire was ascertained by the advisor and one instructor from the Management department of Dambi Dollo University. The questionnaires asked them whether the questions were relevant to the research issues. On the basis of their comments, the researcher revised the contents of the questionnaire before it was used in the study.

Face Validity: Use the respondents to answer the question. This is the subjective view of the respondents to the survey (not experts).

Convergent Validity: Convergent validity of the variable items was ensured by checking inter-item correlation among the items of various variables

4.1. Data Analysis and Interpretation

4.1.1. Descriptive Study of Variables

Table 4.1 Descriptive Study of Variables

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
Career path development	228	2.3004	.75762
Salary consideration	228	4.1763	.71062
Job satisfaction	228	2.4177	.83725
Working environment	228	3.5000	.85030
Emotional engagement	228	2.9307	1.36253
Work-life balance	228	3.7090	.70380
Turnover intention	228	3.8918	.56923
Valid N (listwise)	228		

SoSource: Own survey, 2025.

As per Table 4.1 of Descriptive Statistics, the mean score of the six independent variables and one dependent variable has a value ranging from 2.3004 to 4.1763. Each of the variables has a different number of questions, and each question in each variable has a different result in terms of frequency, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. It can be found in the appendix: A. The mean score of “Career path development” (2.3004) and “job satisfaction” (2.4177), both variables, has a level of agreement of “Disagree”. The mean score of “emotional engagement” (2.9307) and “work environment” (3.5000) is at the level of agreement of “Neutral”. And the mean score of “salary consideration” (4.1763), “work life balance” (3.7090), and “Turnover intention” (3.8918) has a level of agreement of “Agree”.

4.2. Inferential Statistics

In this section, the results of inferential statistics are presented. For the purpose of assessing the objectives of the study, regression analysis was performed. With the aid of these statistical techniques, conclusions are drawn with respect to the research hypothesis.

Normality Test

Normality test of data is applied to determine whether the data is well-modeled by a normal distribution or not, and to compute how likely an underlying random variable is to be normally distributed. Skewness and Kurtosis were used to measure the normality of the data for this study.

Table 4.2. Normality test using Skewness and Kurtosis

	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic
Career path development	.235	.161	.546	.321
Salary consideration	-.510	.161	.946	.321
Job satisfaction	-.769	.161	-.096	.321

Working environment	-.325	.161	.171	.321
Emotional engagement	.016	.161	-.509	.321
Work-life balance	-.288	.161	-.609	.321
Turnover intention	-.201	.161	-.574	.321

Source: Own survey, 2025

George and Mallery (2005) stated that the acceptable range for skewness and kurtosis is ± 1.96 . Therefore, according to this study, the Skewness and Kurtosis of each variable fall within the gap of ± 1.96 . Hence, the data collected is considered normally distributed.

Regression Analysis

In regression analysis, the researcher regresses determinants of employee perceived turnover intention vs. career path development, salary consideration, job satisfaction, working environment, emotional engagement, and work-life balance as independent variables.

Table. 4.3. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.645	.416	.400	.44097	1.589

Source: Own survey, 2025

Predictors: (Constant), career path, development, salary consideration, job satisfaction, working environment, emotional engagement, and work-life balance.

Dependent Variable: Turnover intention.

Analysis of Variance for Dependent and Independent Variables

Table 4.4.ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	30.579	6	5.097	26.210	.000 ^b
Residual	42.974	221	.194		
Total	73.554	227			

Source: Own survey, 2025.

a. Dependent Variable: Turnover intention

b. Predictors: (Constant), career path, development, salary consideration, job satisfaction, working environment, emotional engagement, and work-life balance.

The above Table 4.4 shows the result of the analysis of variance between dependent and independent variables of this study. It reflects that at a 95% level of confidence, the calculated F value of ANOVA is 26.210 at 6 and 221 degrees of freedom, which is greater than the table value (2.4) derived from the F Distribution Table for alpha 0.05. Therefore, by rejecting the H_0 , the H_1 is accepted. This means all six independent variables are significantly affecting the turnover intention based on the analysis of variance table.

Table 4.5. Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	3.740	.338		11.057	.000		
Career path development	-.362	.042	-.482	-8.670	.000	.855	1.169
Salary consideration	.107	.045	.133	2.374	.018	.837	1.194
Job satisfaction	-.098	.035	-.161	-2.837	.005	.817	1.224
Working environment	.045	.041	.067	1.097	.274	.717	1.395
Work life balance	.189	.034	.299	5.564	.000	.913	1.095
Emotional engagement	.031	.022	.075	1.418	.158	.942	1.062

Source: Own survey, 2025

Dependent Variable: Turnover intention

Table 4.6. Test of Hypothesis

	Hypothesis Statement	p-value	Significance	Result
H ₁	Job satisfaction has a significant impact on employees' perceived turnover intention.	0.005	Significant	Accept
H ₂	The workplace environment has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention.	0.274	Insignificant	Reject
H ₃	Career path development has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention.	0.000	Significant	Accept
H ₄	Emotional engagement has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention.	0.158	Insignificant	Reject
H ₅	Salary consideration has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention.	0.018	Significant	Accept
H ₆	Work-life balance has a significant impact on employees' perceived turnover intention.	0.000	Significant	Accept
H ₇	Gender has a significant impact on employees' perceived turnover intention.	0.561	Insignificant	Reject
H ₈	Age has significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention.	0.708	Insignificant	Reject
H ₉	Education level has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention..	0.571	Insignificant	Reject

H ₁₀	Marital status has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention.	0.048	Significant	Accept
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Source: Own survey, 2025

5.1. Conclusion

This study was conducted to examine the determinants of employee perceived turnover intention in private secondary schools in Dambi Dollo Zone. To conduct this study, teachers were taken from all private secondary schools in Dambi Dollo Zone. These schools were Betelhem Secondary school, Chorra Secondary school, Dubo Secondary school, ABBA PASKAL Secondary school, Lika Secondary school, Lutran Secondary school, and Denbosko Secondary school.

Teachers working in private secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone consist of both sexes, with the majority of male teachers. Regarding the composition of the age majority of the private secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone, teachers are in the age range between 21 and 30 years. Teachers working in private secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone consist of a majority of degree holders, and regarding the marital status of teachers, the majority of them are married. The identified independent variables for this study were career path development, salary consideration, job satisfaction, work environment, emotional engagement, and work-life balance. The level of correlation between the dependent variable (turnover intention) and independent variables is concluded as follows: career path development and job satisfaction hurt turnover intention. Whereas salary consideration and work life balance have positive correlation with perceived turnover intention. Career path development, salary consideration, job satisfaction, and work-life balance factors had a significant impact on turnover intention, while emotional engagement and work environment factors were found to be insignificant factors for employee perceived turnover intention of private secondary schools of Dambi Dollo Zone. Career path development was found to have the greatest impact, followed by work-life balance, job satisfaction, and salary consideration. Sex, age, and level of education of teachers have an insignificant impact on employee perceived turnover intention. It was found that the marital status of teachers has a significant impact on employee perceived turnover intention.

5.2. Recommendation

Based on the findings, discussions, and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are forwarded to the management and school administrators of private secondary schools in Dambi Dollo Zone.

- The management and school administrators should look into the areas of teachers' career path development by facilitating training and development programs and providing scope for better advancement. The management and school administrators should also provide adequate opportunities for the promotion and upgradation of the teachers for better positions. These factors will subsequently reduce the intention of teachers to quit their jobs since career path development has the highest impact on the turnover intention in this study.
- The salary consideration factor was found to be highly responsible for reducing the turnover intention of teachers to leave their jobs. Hence the management and school administrators should consider the salary consideration issues. They should pay a sufficient salary that matches other equivalent qualifications in other industries. Teachers should be paid a fair salary for the job they are doing, and incentives and other benefits should also be provided. The salary paid for teachers should be reasonable.
- The management and school administrators should look into job satisfaction factors of their employees. It is recommended that the immediate superiors should give recognition to teachers

for their achievements, create a favorable and achievable functioning of the school, and create opportunities to involve teachers in the activities of the school. Hence, by improving these job satisfaction factors, the intention of teachers to quit their jobs can be reduced.

- The management and school administrators should give due recognition to the life balance of their employees. They should reduce work pressure to allow teachers to enjoy their personal lives. The amount of leisure time given to teachers should be reasonable. The management and school administrators should consider the feelings of teachers to balance both their personal life and their work lives. By improving the work-life balance factors, it can reduce the turnover intention of teachers to quit their jobs.

5.3. Directions for Further Research

This study included only six determinants of employee turnover intention; there could be many other relevant determinants that may be perceived as important factors of employee turnover intention, like job characteristics, job demands, job resources, job stress, lack of equipment, poor communication, lack of motivation, etc... But those were excluded from this study. Future research, therefore, may consider more determinants of employee turnover intention factors.

Furthermore, conducting a replication study in other manufacturing and service industries and other parts of the country is also needed. For example, in the production sector, hotel service, telecommunication service, post office service, banking service, hospitals, and so on.

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